

Iterating particle mixings

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The fundamental theorem for doubly stochastic matrices **[1]** ensures their iterates eventually become constant; formally, if S is $m \times m$ doubly stochastic

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} S^n = (1/m)J_m$$

where J_m is the $m \times m$ matrix of all 1's. Since elementary particle mixing matrices are doubly stochastic **[2]** how quickly does this happen? Let's see.

2D

Here

$$S(\theta) = \begin{pmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta \end{pmatrix}$$

For the Cabibbo angle 13.04° this becomes

$$S(13.04^\circ) = \begin{pmatrix} 0.9490905443934892 & 0.0509094556065107 \\ 0.0509094556065107 & 0.9490905443934892 \end{pmatrix}$$

which reaches $(1/2)J_2$ at about $n=2,000$ OCTAVE iterations. Similarly, for the Neutrino angle 33.41°

$$S(33.41^\circ) = \begin{pmatrix} 0.696810523419162 & 0.303189476580838 \\ 0.303189476580838 & 0.696810523419162 \end{pmatrix}$$

which reaches $(1/2)J_2$ much more quickly, at about $n=40$ OCTAVE iterations, 50 times faster.

3D

The Maiani/Chau/Keung doubly stochastic matrix **[2]** will be used to estimate convergence of its iterates; as usual

$$C_j = \cos\theta_j \text{ and } S_j = \sin\theta_j, j = 1,2,3.$$

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} c_1^2 c_3^2 & c_3^2 s_1^2 & s_3^2 \\ c_2^2 s_1^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_1^2 c_2^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 s_3^2 & c_3^2 s_2^2 \\ c_1^2 c_2^2 s_3^2 + s_1^2 s_2^2 & c_2^2 s_1^2 s_3^2 + c_1^2 s_2^2 & c_2^2 c_3^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

In Quark-mixing, angle estimates are **[3]**:

$$\theta_1 = 13.04^\circ = 0.2276 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_2 = 2.38^\circ = 0.0415 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_3 = .201^\circ = 0.0035 \text{ rad}$$

so the probability matrix is

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} 0.9490788641279793 & 0.0509088290741298 & 0.0000123067978907 \\ 0.0508216832724636 & 0.9474538552306898 & 0.0017244614968464 \\ 0.0000994525995569 & 0.0016373156951802 & 0.9982632317052628 \end{pmatrix}$$

which is close to $(1/3)J_3$ after some 20,000 OCTAVE iterations.

As for Neutrino-mixing, angle estimates are **[4]**

$$\theta_1 = 33.41^\circ = .5831 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_2 = 49.1^\circ = .8569 \text{ rad}$$

$$\theta_3 = 8.54^\circ = .1491 \text{ rad}$$

The probability matrix is now

$$S = \begin{pmatrix} 0.6814443170017583 & 0.2965034809993340 & 0.0220522019989076 \\ 0.1387518784395988 & 0.3025323967355806 & 0.5587157248248205 \\ 0.1798038045586428 & 0.4009641222650854 & 0.4192320731762718 \end{pmatrix}$$

which is close to $(1/3)J_3$ after only 50 OCTAVE iterations, some 400 times faster.

What is the connection, if any, between particle decay rates and iteration convergence speed?

References

[1] J.G. Kemeny, J.L. Snell, Finite Markov Chains, Van Nostrand, 1960.

- [2]** A. Cusmariu, 'Mixing strategies and Hadamard products in elementary particle physics', zenodo.8404365, 2013.
- [3]** Wikipedia article on 'Cabbibo-Kobayashi-Maskawa matrix'.
- [4]** Wikipedia article on 'Pontecorvo-Maki-Nakagawa-Sakata matrix'.